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A self-evaluation exercise of impact of a social innovation initiative in a rural area of southern Italy

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Summary

Although the concept of SI in agriculture is relatively recent, EU has already shown interest in the approach and a willingness to invest in innovative social projects. In the field of agriculture, the most common social innovation initiatives that have emerged in the latest years are either linked to social farming or community supported agriculture. These initiatives aim at exploiting the multifunctionality of agriculture activities, coupling productive agricultural activities with educational, caregiving, or inclusive services, in the former; and connecting consumers and producers in direct informal relationships in the latter. Despite the growing interest in social innovation in the field of agriculture, literature lacks validated tools for evaluating social innovations. This work provides an empirical application of the evaluation approach to the SI in Marginalised Rural Areas as developed by the SIMRA consortium. It is as a pilot experience which demonstrates as the evaluation framework actually works and which results is able to produce in terms of monitoring of critical points and strengths of the initiative. According to our findings, the overall distribution of the indicators, show positive picture of the SI, where the adopted indicators detected strengths and weaknesses of the project. Behind the positive evaluation, this enable us to identifying some issues which requires a special focus to be improved. This information will be helpful to specific categories of actors, who are responsible for the project management. On the contrary, the correct identification of strengths may be useful for actors who are responsible for communication and community engagement. In addition, policy makers may also be interested in grasping the potential of the SI in terms of possible outcomes.

Keywords: Social Innovation, Rural area, Self evaluation, REISS assessment

JEL Classification codes: H43; O13

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Introduction

Agricultural activities are one of the main economic and social drivers of rural areas across Europe (European Commission, 2018). They provide essential business and employment opportunities for the vast majority of rural populations, playing a major role in rural economies. This is especially true for economically marginalized and peripherally remote areas, where agriculture is often one of the last remaining activities that support fighting depopulation and brain drain. In an interconnected and changing world, traditional and rural agricultural economies are asked to reconfigure themselves, embracing innovation (Peters et al., 2018). Innovation is seen as an essential disruptive process, which can enable farmers to develop new products and services able to generate value in new transformed economic systems, strengthening the links between rural and urban markets. In rural areas, inclusive and innovative approaches able to generate new products and services are often coupled with bottom-up inclusive approaches tackling community problems (e.g. depopulation, aging population, land abandonment, etc.) (Bock, 2012). These initiatives are defined as social innovations.

Murray et al. (2010) defines social innovation (SI) as “...new ideas (products, services and models) that simultaneously meet social needs (more effectively than alternatives) and create new social relationships or collaborations. ...they are innovations that are both good for society and enhance society’s capacity to act. The interest is in innovations that are social both in their ends and in their means.” Within the project SIMRA¹, SI is defined as “The reconfiguring of social practices, in response to societal challenges, which seeks to enhance outcomes on societal well-being and necessarily includes the engagement of civil society actors.” (Polman, et al., 2017). This definition takes a closer look to the processes behind social innovation, highlighting the key role of human agency in transforming existing attitudes, social networks, or governance arrangements as to ameliorate the collective well-being of the community.

Although the concept of SI in agriculture is relatively recent, EU has already shown interest in the approach and a willingness to invest in innovative social projects. In the field of agriculture, the most common social innovation initiatives that have emerged in the latest years are either linked to social farming or community supported agriculture (e.g. Gramm et al., 2019; Blättel-Mink et al., 2017). These initiatives aim at exploiting the multifunctionality of agriculture activities, coupling productive agricultural activities with educational, caregiving, or inclusive services, in the former; and connecting

¹ Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas (SIMRA), a project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

consumers and producers in direct informal relationships in the latter. Moreover, the emergence of agricultural hubs both for consumers (e.g. food hubs; Matson et al., 2013) or producers is also common in rural areas, as a way of fostering knowledge exchange and peer-to-peer practices. Despite the growing interest in social innovation in the field of agriculture, literature lacks validated tools for evaluating social innovations. This work provides an empirical application of the evaluation approach to the SI in Marginalised Rural Areas as developed by the SIMRA consortium. It is as a pilot experience which demonstrates as the evaluation framework actually works and which results is able to produce in terms of monitoring of critical points and strengths of the initiative. This is useful to all parties involved in social innovation process, as project manager, innovators, followers and adopters to enable the coordination and focussing efforts. In addition it provides a strong basis to consolidate and expand the engagement of the civil society which is the a crucial prerequisite for SI sustainability.

The case study is represented by VaZapp' (Palumbo, 2015; Lombardi, 2017; Martina, 2017), a rural hub based in the Apulia Region (South Italy) aiming to connect young farmers and to encourage knowledge exchange through the creation of relationships. The analysis will apply the REEIS (relevance, effectiveness, efficiency, impact and sustainability) dimensions by focusing on how many targets have been accomplished (effectiveness), their relevance, whether such targets have been achieved in an optimal way (efficiency), the main impacts generated, and whether these interventions are economically and socially sustainable in the near future.

Material and methods

Context and case study

VaZapp' operates at the level of municipalities located within the Province of Foggia, Apulia region, Italy². The Province of Foggia is defined by a NUTS 3 unit, located in the Italian "Mezzogiorno". It is a "Convergence region" with a Gross Domestic Product per inhabitant of less than 75% of the European Union average. The average income is approximately 8,931 Euros per capita (almost half that of Rome, 15,856 Euros; 45% of Milan, 20,084 Euros). According to Eurostat, the youth unemployment rate in the 15 to 24 age group is 58%, compared to 34.1% for Italy and 19.4% for the Eurozone. This represents a very serious social situation. According to the ranking of the quality of life (newspaper "Il Sole 24 ore"), in 2016 Foggia ranked 102 out of 110 cities (dropping down the rankings since 2014). According to the SVIMEZ report (2014), public expenditure in this area is approximately 25% of the public expenditure

² Currently, the VaZapp' has held contadinnars in 13 municipalities, specifically Apricena, Ascoli Satriano, Biccari, Bovino, Cerignola, Foggia, Orta Nova, San Giovanni Rotondo, San Nicandro Garganico, San Severo, Stornara, Stornarella, Zapponeta.

in the northern Italian regions. This leads to very low outcomes in terms of the amount and quality of services and a low quality of life. Private firms operate in difficult conditions, hindering their competitiveness in domestic and foreign markets. As a whole, the Province of Foggia comprises 61 municipalities, with a total population of 630,581 inhabitants and a total area of 7,008 km² (Fig.1) The mean population density is 89.98 persons/km² (1st January 2016). Foggia is the Italian province with the highest extent of arable land in Italy (495,111 ha), but farmers have a low level of education (70% of them did not finish compulsory education), and only 4% of the total of farmers are young farmers.

Figure 1. Location of the study area. Source: Own elaboration based on Google Maps data.

Even though VàZapp' was officially established in 2014, the origin of this Social Innovation dates back to the meeting in October 2009 between the future founder of VàZapp' and a very active priest operating in the social context of the Province. After the meeting, the founder and another future innovator attended the various activities of the priest, in which they acknowledged the needs and disadvantages of local young people and their lack of hope towards the future. The interaction between the founder and the priest progressively intensified until the death of the latter which marked the definitive passage of the baton to the future social innovator, who inherited the mission of supporting local young people in realizing their dreams without emigrating.

The main idea of this social initiative was born in 2014, with *Oliday*, the first official event organized by VàZapp' group, which consisted in an olives oil harvesting day in a local farm, a typical farming activity of the area in the autumn period which is well rooted in the local culture. This event involved many (about 30) non-farmers young people close to the movement of the priest. In the same period, the core group of actors starting the initiative, decided to establish a formal association, namely "*Terra promessa*" to regulate the interaction among VàZapp' members and to register the VàZapp' as a

trademark (Lombardi M., 2017). From November 2014 to December 2015, the founders and the followers organised a series of 4 spot events in different local farms. These events prepared the ground for the build of the social innovation prototype in the final format of the first *Contadinner* in December 2015, where about 30 young people of the province of Foggia participated. This first event can be considered as the beginning of the VàZapp' project phase.

From December 2015 to March 2018, 18 *Contadinner*s have been organised. The project is structured into a 20-20-20 format, which stands for 20 dinners, 20 farms, 20 young farmers organized. They aim of gathering about 400 young farmers around the same table, after dinner, hearing from them and sharing life experiences, projects and knowledge in agriculture. On July 2016 the network of VàZapp' established a cooperative named "Terra Terra", the juridical tool for the operation of VàZapp'. Its formal objective is to provide extension services. VàZapp' members used this tool to arrange and hold *contadinner* (Lombardi, 2017). The *Contadinner*s caused positive changes in attitudes and networks of community. In particular, VàZapp' recorded new openness and confidence attitude among its participants proven that they feel free to speak about their personal experience, express their fears, share dreams, that is something they never shared with others before. The initiative is leaving its earlier phase to enter in a more defined and mature configuration.

Figure 2. Chronology of the Social Innovation ‘V&Zapp’ in the province of Foggia (Italy). Own elaboration.

Data collection and analysis

A combination of qualitative and quantitative data collection tools developed by SIMRA (Secco *et al.*, 2018) were applied to the case study (Secco *et al.*, 2019; Górriz-Mifsud *et al.* 2018), including semi-structured interviews (open questions, storytelling), structured interviews (questionnaires with open and closed questions), a focus group, and context indicators. Data was collected through 44 direct interviews conducted in a 6 months period (April-September 2018). The survey concerned different categories of

actors (innovators, followers, transformers and beneficiaires), table 1 reports the respondents per each category.

Table 1 - Survey structure

Actors category	Category definition	N. of respondents
Innovator	Key leaders and first drivers of innovation. Innovators are identifiable individuals who had the idea, invented it, discovered it or were attracted to it	2
Follower	The first to adopt or support the idea of the innovator, they can be co-creators or identify a good idea and identify a practical approach to carry it forward	9
Transformer	People who adopt an idea at an early stage and spread it to other people in the network	17
Direct Beneficiary	The people benefiting directly from the outputs and outcomes of the social innovation	10

Source : Secco et al., 2019 ; Secco et al, 2018

The quantitative analysis has been conducted according to the Handbook of SI indicators developed by SIMRA for the evaluation of social innovation cases (Secco *et al.*, 2019); which provides guidance on the interpretation of results. This information has been complemented with the qualitative data from the focus group and semi-structured interviews, and analysed according to the qualitative reporting tools. By merging the data collected by different tools, is possible to assess the social innovation in terms of Relevance, Efficiency, Effectiveness, Impact and Sustainability (REEIS assessment of the Social Innovation) and assessment of Social Innovation according to SIMRA definition. In particular, it aims at verifying whether:

- The objectives set up in the social innovation are satisfying the needs of the territory and of the actors involved (Relevance);
- The outputs of the social innovation have been achieved with few inputs in terms of resources (costs and time) (Efficiency);
- The outputs achieved satisfy the initial objectives (Effectiveness);
- The extent to which the social innovation initiative have created impacts on environment, society, economy and governance (Impacts);
- The extent to which the social innovation initiative is sustainable, thus measuring the likelihood for the benefits produced to continue to flow after the external funding has ended, with particular reference to their economic and social factors (Sustainability).

The analysis is based on quantitative indicators, and their triangulation with qualitative statements.

Data on budgets are also used to assess the efficiency of the initiative.

Results

The results of the data analysis are reported in Table 2. Within the overall group of 40 indicators, 31 of them (78%) have been applied, while 9 indicators (22%) could not be calculated, due to the lack of related information. The last column of the table reports the performance of SI initiative in qualitative terms. The qualitative rating is expressed along a three degrees scale of performance based on the distribution of the indicators score, namely *high* (third tertile) *medium* (second tertile), and *low* (first tertile). The most part of indicators belong the *high* (%) and medium categories (%).

Table 2 – Results of self-evaluation exercise

DIMENSION	Indicator	Results	Range	Perform.
Relevance	R1. Consistency with European societal challenges	45.5	[0-100]	M
	R2. Shared needs within the Social Innovation network	23.8	[0-100]	L
	R3. Shared vision regarding collective needs	44	[0-100]	M
	R4. Consistency of Social Innovation project with European societal challenges	NA ^a	[0-100]	-
	R5. Beneficiaries' extent (level) of satisfaction with their needs	7	[1-10]	H
	R6. Capacity of the Social Innovation project to address beneficiaries' needs	1.2	[0-3]	M
	R7. Extent (level) of satisfaction with territorial needs	7.3 ^b	[1-10]	H
	^a Due to the lack of Tool 5 this indicator was not calculated ^b Due to the lack of Tool 5 this indicator was built only with Tool 3 and 4 data.			
Efficiency	E1. Cost per network actor in the Social Innovation process	88651.4	[0-inf]	
	E2. Satisfaction with Invested Resources (SIR), Social Innovation process	1.7	[0.1-10]	L
	E3. Efficiency of the Social Innovation process	1.5	[0.1-10]	L
	E4. Unit cost per beneficiary of the Social Innovation project	15.8 ^a	[0-inf]	
	E5. Unit cost per Network's actor in the Social Innovation project	69168.9	[0-inf]	
	E6. Time goals respected	NA ^b	[1-4]	
	E7. Budget goals respected	NA ^b	[1-4]	
	E8. Unit cost per person involved in the Social Innovation initiative	5813.3 ^c	[0-inf]	
	^a Due to the lack of Tool 5 this indicator was calculated using the total number of beneficiaries as estimated by the evaluator (400, Table 1). ^b Due to the lack of Tool 5 this indicator was not calculated ^c Due to the lack of Tool 5 this indicator was built only with Tool 1, 3, and 4 data, and it was calculated using the total number of beneficiaries as estimated by the evaluator (400, Table 1).			

Effectiveness	F1. Expected vs. observed changes in the Social Innovation process	58.1	[0-100]	M
	F2. (Extent of) Perceived changes in the reconfiguration due to the Social Innovation process	7.2	[1-10]	H
	F3. Reconfigured collaborative network	0.18	[-1; +1]	M
	F4. Reconfigured governance arrangement	5 ^a	[0-6]	H
	F5. Level of beneficiaries' satisfaction with the Social Innovation project's results	7.5	[1-10]	H
	F6. Identified vs. delivered products and services of the SI project	40	[0-100]	M
	F7. New relations of the partners and beneficiaries of the SI project	1.4 ^b	[0-100]	L
	F8. New beneficiaries reached thanks to the Social Innovation Project	NA ^c	[0-100]	
	F9. Evaluation by project partners of achievement of objectives	NA ^c	[1-3]	
	F10. Effectiveness of the communication channels of the Social Innovation project	27.5	[0-100]	L
	F11. Actors' perception of being able to make a difference with the Social Innovation initiative	7.9	[1-10]	H
	^a The indicator was not assessed as new governance arrangements were not one of VàZapp' objectives indicated during FG (Session II). ^b Due to the lack of Tool 5 this indicator was built only with Tool 6 data. ^c Due to the lack of Tool 5 this indicator was not calculated. ^d Due to the lack of Tool 5 this indicator was built only with Tool 3,4, and 6 data.			
Impacts	I3. Reduced level of marginalization [perception]	NA ^a	[1-10]	
	I4. Governance improvement due to the Social Innovation project	NA ^a	[0-100]	
	I5. Social inclusion due to the Social Innovation project	NA ^a	[0-100]	
	I6. Impact of the Social Innovation project in terms of number of final beneficiaries	17.4	[0-inf]	
	I7. European societal challenges' improvement in the territory due to the Social Innovation project	NA ^a	[0-100]	
	I8. Reduced level of marginalization	0	[0-100]	L
	I9. Marginalization reduction indexes	0 ^b	[0-100]	L
	I10. Positive impacts of the Social Innovation initiative on environmental, economic, social and institutional/governance elements	100	[0-100]	H
	I11. Balance between the positive and negative impacts of the Social Innovation initiative on the four domains	MAX ^c	[0-inf]	H
		^a Due to the lack of Tool 5 this indicator was not calculated. ^b No marginalization constraints have been improved thanks to VàZapp' due to its limited sphere of influence in the local territory. ^c No negative elements have been identified in the interviews. ^d Due to the lack of Tool 5 this indicator was built only with Tool 3 and 6 data.		
Sustainability	S1. Economic self-sufficiency of the Social Innovation process	99.8	[0-100]	H
	S2. Likelihood of benefits produced by the Social Innovation project to continue to flow in the future	74.5 ^a	[0-inf]	

	S3. Socio-economic sustainability of the Social Innovation project	66.7 ^a	[0-100]	M
	S4. Financial dependence of the Social Innovation budget upon internal resources	100 ^b	[0-100]	H
	S5. Financial sustainability of the Social Innovation project	4.3 ^a	[1-6]	H
	^a Due to the lack of Tool 5 this indicator was built only with Tool 3 data.			
	^b Due to the lack of Tool 5 this indicator was built only with Tool 1 and 3 data.			

Source: own elaborations

Note. Score tertile: L=low; M=medium; H=High

The results of each individual indicator in relation to the 5 dimensions will be discussed in detail below.

Relevance. The objectives set by innovators and followers in the early phases of the social innovation process match at about 46% those of the European societal challenges (R1). They refers mainly to the following challenges: Income, jobs, education, Sustainable agriculture and food security, Inclusive societies, and Innovative societies Concerning the internal relevance of VàZapp' Social Innovation process (R2), this initiative scores 24%, showing that less than a third of the early needs are aligned with those emerged at a second stage within the network. About 44% of the network members share the same vision of collective needs of those of the clique (R3), which are: a) To restore dignity to local and traditional agriculture and to the role of the farmer; b) to give hope to the young generation , bringing them closer to the agricultural world and providing them job opportunities. The project of this SI is the creation of a rural bub, by means of a cycle of 20 farmers' dinner. VàZapp' services appear to positively satisfy existing beneficiaries' needs, with a mean score of 7 out of 10 (R5). Regarding beneficiaries' needs, about one in three are perceived to be satisfied by the outputs of the initiative (R6), with the most commons being the need of creating new relationships and cooperate with existing local actors (mentioned by 40% of the beneficiaries), and the possibility of exchanging ideas, technical solutions, and cultural proposals (mentioned by 30% of the beneficiaries). The whole initiative from its conception until its current configuration has a high perceived relevance (R7), indicating a good satisfaction of VàZapp' actors (Innovator, followers, transformers, mainstreamers and project partners) with respect to the territorial needs. Additionally, VàZapp' is perceived as capable to address the majority of beneficiaries' needs.

Efficiency. The amount of resources invested in the SI process per participant in VàZapp' is 88651 € (E1) indicating a high number of both monetary and personal (above all) invested resources in the project activities. The efficiency of VàZapp' scores low when considering the level of actors' satisfaction with the resources invested in the SI process (E2). However, the most part of the resources invested are in the form of volunteer work directed at arranging and carrying out the farmers' dinner. This means that, in addition to network members, many other people have benefited from these efforts. As a consequence, to have a complete idea of the VàZapp' efficiency, these resources should be referred to the beneficiaries of the farmers' dinners that are 400, rather than to the small group of 28 network members. While the

level of satisfaction with the first steps V`Zapp' moved in the territory scores high, the resources invested are perceived as moderate, dragging down the overall satisfaction. This similarly affects the overall efficiency of the Social Innovation process (E3), due to the large amount of resources invested compared to the overall intangible outputs obtained.

On the contrary, the level of financial and material resources is perceived lower, respectively as an average of 3.8 on a scale of 10. This indicates how the network of actors was actively engaged in establishing the first steps of the initiative and mainly with voluntarily work. The costs of the SI project per direct beneficiary is equal to 15.8 € (E4) when calculated on the average total yearly cost of V`Zapp' for the last three years, and 400 people as estimated beneficiaries. The Unit cost per Network's actor (N=28) is equal to 69169 € (E5), similarly for the process, due to the continuous dedicated efforts (mainly in kind) of the network of V`Zapp'. As mentioned above, in terms of whether the project was successful in meeting its goals it should be bear in mind that the most part of the resources invested was directed at gather people within the farmers' dinners. Moreover, proven that the most part of the resources are in the form of volunteer work, V`Zapp' did not face financial and budget related constraints. The unit yearly cost of V`Zapp' per actor involved is of 5813€/year (E8). The Unit cost per Network's actor (N=28) of the overall initiative is higher than what estimated for only the SI project again due to the overall level of in kind contributions of the actors.

Effectiveness. The congruence between expected and observed changes is above average (F1), with about 58% of the expectations matching the realizations, especially in relation to the new realized network. The survey results estimate a 72% share of perceived changes thanks to the Social Innovation process (F2). In particular, informants assigned highest values to respectively new relationships established (average of 8.5 over 10), and the improved inclusiveness of the network (8.4 over 10). V`Zapp' network changes are also supported by the results of the SNAs, highlighting a positive change of density (18%) of the network collaboration after the organisation of the first Contadinner (F3).

In terms of effectiveness of the SI project, results suggest a large beneficiaries' satisfaction with what V`Zapp' was able to move forward (F6), with about 40% of the products and services identified at early stages delivered by the project (e.g. creation of new relationships and information sharing initiatives). About 1.4% new relationships across beneficiaries were established thanks to V`Zapp' (F7). The effectiveness of the communication channels (F10) is instead quite low, scoring highest for social media (Facebook), and regular media being able to reach respectively 60% and 30% of V`Zapp' beneficiaries. Informal channels as words of mouths appear to be equally effective (50%). The effectiveness of the overall initiative appears to be high (7.9 on a scale of 10), with a perception of the local actors sensing that they were making a difference in the territory (F11).

Impact. The initiative reaches a moderate number of final indirect beneficiaries by estimating about 17 (I6), which cover mainly friends and relatives of those farmers that started to benefit from V`Zapp'

effects. When assessing the perception collected during the focus group on the reduced marginalization thanks to V`aZapp', the results show that the majority of the physical, infrastructural, and socio-economic constraints are inexistent or stable before and after the creation of the initiative in the province (I8). Concerning the elements that the initiative has impacted in the four domains (environmental, economic, social and institutional), the results of the focus group discussion show that no negative elements have been identified (I10, I11).

Sustainability. V`aZapp' is estimated by the informants to possibly last for more than 70 years in the future, suggesting an important sustainability of this type of projects in the Province of Foggia (S2). Moreover, in socio-economic terms, this initiative is perceived to be sustainable (S3), and mainly in social terms rather than economic ones. The main social factors that make the project more likely to survive are: the fact that the Social Innovation is based on the engagement of highly motivated people ready to work voluntarily (as presented above all the clique members worked fully voluntary in the early phases of the project), and that V`aZapp' resolves a central problem of the community (modernizing the agricultural sector of the province). As mentioned in the previous sub-section, the percentage of external resources estimated by the informant is almost zero (S4). However the budget computed indicates that about 14% of V`aZapp' resources came from external funding in the form of rent of location for 2 special events covered by a local public institution. This inconsistency is due to the fact that the informant, while replying, was focused on the cash flow, while in this case the public funding was provided by annulling the rent due for the location. This is further proved by indicator S5 indicating a high perceived financial sustainability of the project V`aZapp'.

Discussion

In order to summarize the results derived from the REEIS assessment, we aggregated the number of indicators contained in the same tertile, and we obtained the summary represented in Table 3.

Table 3 - REEIS assessment values

CRITERIA	VALUE
Relevance	14% L - 43%M - 29%H
Efficiency	25% L - 0% M - 0% H
Effectiveness	18% L - 27%M - 36%H
Impacts	22% L - 0%M - 22% H

Sustainability	0% L - 20% M - 60% H
TOTAL	18% L - 18% M - 28%H

According to the overall distribution of the indicators, it is possible to grasp a positive picture of the SI, where strengths (number of indicators whose score belongs to the top tertile) are relevant, with respect to weaknesses (that is, indicators referred to the first tertile). Behind the positive evaluation, this enable us to identifying some issues which requires a special focus to be improved.

This information will be helpful to specific categories of actors, who are responsible for the project management. On the contrary, the correct identification of strengths may be useful for actors who are responsible for communication and community engagement. In addition, policy makers may also be interested in grasping the potential of the SI in terms of possible outcomes.

More specifically, each criteria can be useful to different actors, who may focus on future actions to improve the SI. In particular:

relevance: can be used by public relations to evaluate and finally communicate the capacity of the project project to address the needs and satisfaction of beneficiaries;

efficiency: administration and control of the economic sustainability and financial viability;

effectiveness: project manager;

impacts: communication to community and policy makers, aimed at fostering the public engagement and fundraising;

sustainability: project designer committed in the development, reinforcement and (eventually) replication of the SI.

In this way, the large plethora of indicators may provide a comprehensive information regarding the present situation, addressing specific information needs.

Conclusions

The main lesson learnt from this case study has potentially strong implication: even in areas plagued by great socio-economic problems (as a severe economic crisis with related dramatic level of youth unemployment rates) emigration is not the only way out, on the contrary reaction is possible. Of course, this reaction is not directly operating on the general economic issues affecting the entire Country, as this requires operating at a wider scale by means of policy instruments. Instead, V&Zapp' operates reverting the cultural basis of the countermeasure against the economic measures (traditionally emigration) by creating acceptance for people who decided to stay. The main way to do this was creating and reinforcing a linkage between the rural status and the urban communities by means of social events. In

this way VàZapp' tackles to the root of the problem, which is restore the dignity to local and traditional agriculture and emancipation of young people. This finally resulted in turn into enthusiasm among young farmers, capacity of co-working, and eventually into the creation of career opportunities for skilled people.

Another major finding of this study is that the conditions for reaction to occur and the causality between trigger and social innovation are not trivial (trigger -> social needs -> social innovation) but require an actual alignment of specific factors, that, in this case were: (i) a long-time accumulation process resulting in needs matching with some personal qualities of the innovators (e.g. strong friendship and spiritual link), and theirs' communication and professional skills (i.e. human capital); (ii) a pre-existing network of people (i.e. social capital) and a context condition that favoured the social networking. This enabled the movement to rise spontaneously, without external financial capital, and with the direct involvement of existing human and social capital. To transform, accumulate and employ this immaterial forms of capital, VàZapp' exhibited some level of closure which allowed for the establishment of specific rules, vision and governance style (which are normative and cognitive components of the social capital).

Finally, VàZapp' by straddling profit and non-profit domains in producing its outputs, generated a hybridisation model. On one hand, events and relations promotion are produced at non-profit level. On the other hand, these relations lead to the establishment of professional agreements which belongs to the private sector.

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